

Abstraction in Computer Music Software Systems

by

Günter Geiger

Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for
the degree of Diploma of Advanced Studies
Doctorate in Computer Science and Digital Communication
Department of Technology

Tutor: Dr. Xavier Serra

Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Barcelona, July 2005

Abstract

In its almost 50 years of existence the field of computer music has brought us dozens of software systems, and new ones are still being added. This is a sign of the field's vitality and of constant interest in improving the tools that are used in order to make music on computers.

This work is primarily an overview of existing systems, from a conceptual point of view, in an attempt to extract the essence of computer music systems and to pinpoint the software models that work best in the computer music domain. The criteria are flexibility, speed and - drawn from human computer interaction - intuitiveness of the programming model.

Secondarily it is a review of my research work in this direction and finally an attempt to reassemble the best ideas into a consistent, fast, flexible and easy to use interactive computer music system that foments experimentation and creativity.

The domain of this work is very broad and it can't give all the answers, but it hopefully manage to ask the right questions.

Contents

1	Introduction	9
1.1	Motivation and Context	9
1.2	Computer Music Systems	10
1.3	Programming Languages	11
1.4	Using and Programming	12
2	Computer Music Systems Review	14
2.1	From Music I to GROOVE	14
2.2	Music-N Descendants	15
2.3	Control Languages	17
2.4	Realtime Control Systems, Sequencers	18
2.5	General Purpose High Level Languages	20
2.6	Realtime DSP Languages	22
2.7	Current Developments	23
2.8	Conclusion	25
3	Computer Music System Concepts	27
3.1	General Concepts	28
3.1.1	The UnitGenerator	28
3.1.2	Data Centered Signal Processing	30

3.1.3	The Score	32
3.1.4	Instrument Description and Syntax	33
3.1.5	Polyphony	35
3.2	Setup and Control	36
3.2.1	Score Generation	37
3.2.2	Event Generation and Processing	37
3.2.3	Orchestra Generation	38
3.3	Performance Optimization	39
3.3.1	Performance Bottlenecks	39
3.3.2	Signal and Control Rate	40
3.3.3	Control Signals versus Events	41
3.3.4	Table Lookup	41
3.3.5	Block Computation	42
3.4	Algorithm Related Concepts	44
3.4.1	Wavetables	44
3.4.2	Delay and Delaylines	45
3.4.3	Feedback	45
3.4.4	Granular Synthesis	46
3.5	Implementation Details	47
3.5.1	Static Scheduling	47
3.5.2	Dynamic Scheduling	49
3.5.3	DSP Memory Management	52
3.6	Higher Level Concepts	53
3.6.1	Hierarchical Structure	53
3.6.2	Signal - Control Duality	55
3.6.3	Higher Level Data Handling	55
3.7	Language Concepts	56

3.7.1	Domain Specific Languages	57
3.7.2	Functional Programming	57
3.7.3	Object Oriented Programming	57
3.8	Conclusions	58
4	Design and Implementation	59
4.1	Goals of a Computer Music System	59
4.1.1	Target User	59
4.1.2	Intuitiveness	60
4.1.3	Incremental Development	60
4.1.4	Extensibility	60
4.1.5	Interaction	61
4.1.6	Portability	61
4.1.7	Efficiency	61
4.1.8	Research	62
4.1.9	Musical Openness	62
4.2	Drawbacks of Existing Systems	62
4.2.1	Text Based Languages and Interaction	62
4.2.2	The Graphical Programming Paradigm	63
4.2.3	Complexity	63
4.3	Putting it together	63
4.3.1	The Interface	63
4.3.2	The Language	64
4.3.3	Concurrency	65
4.3.4	Design of Basic Building Blocks	65
4.4	Three studies: Toluene, ALUA and AudioBlocks	65
4.4.1	Toluene	66
4.4.2	ALUA	68

4.4.3	AudioBlocks	70
5	Future Work	73
5.1	Implementation Details	73
5.2	Just-in-time Programming	74
5.3	Programming Languages	75
5.4	Conclusions	76
A	Interpreter for Signal Processing	77
A.1	Abstract	77
A.2	Introduction	78
A.3	Implementation Considerations	79
A.3.1	Threading [30, 40]	80
A.3.2	Stack Caching	81
A.3.3	Common Interpreters	81
A.4	An Interpreter for Signal Processing	82
A.4.1	The Floating Point Stack	83
A.4.2	Parsing	83
A.4.3	Type and Memory Checks	84
A.5	Results	84
A.6	Conclusion	86
B	PDA	88
B.1	Abstract	88
B.2	Introduction	89
B.3	Handheld Devices	90
B.3.1	Sound Quality	90
B.3.2	Processing Power	91
B.3.3	Memory and Peripherals	92

B.4	Computer Music on PocketPC	92
B.4.1	PD and Linux	92
B.4.2	The Performance	92
B.4.3	Programming with PDA	93
B.4.4	Controlling the System	94
B.5	Future Directions	94
B.6	Conclusions	95

List of Figures

1.1	CSound sine tone	11
1.2	CLM sine tone	11
1.3	Pure Data sine tone	12
1.4	SuperCollider sine tone	12
3.1	A unit generator diagram	28
3.2	Code for adding 2 Wave's in Toluene	31
3.3	example Music V orchestra and score	32
3.4	example of low level loop unrolling technique	43
3.5	delayline and delay reader - single delay UG	46
3.6	A filtered noise example with STK	48
3.7	DSP graph of a modified karplus strong resonator	48
3.8	function call implementation in ALUA	50
3.9	A block based representation of a "patch"	54
4.1	FFT - IFFT calculation using Toluene	67
4.2	ALUA program for playing an FM line	69
4.3	FM synthesis AudioBlocks patch	71
A.1	Performance of the FIR filter	85
A.2	Performance of Scaling for different optimization settings	85

A.3 Performance of the Peak picking algorithm for different optimization settings	86
---	----

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation and Context

Systems for producing music with computers have a long tradition, the focus of this work is to extract the ideas from computer music systems that exist now and have existed in the past, systems that have influenced our way of thinking about computer music.

I have been working in the computer music field for several years, mainly as a programmer, less as a musician and performer. I got my degree (Diplom Ingenieur) from the University of Technology in Graz, Austria where I have been working at the Institute for Electronic Music (IEM) during my studies. After a year of implementation programming in C++ at the Philips Speech Processing laboratory in Vienna I started working as an independent consultant and programmer for several sound and multimedia installations in museums and public spaces.

I was using free software applications in a professional context and I became contributor to some Free Software projects, for example by porting the computer music system Pure Data [51] and its graphical extension li-

brary Gem [14] to Linux and contributing to both systems and by writing a soundcard driver for the Linux Kernel.

I joined the Music Technology Group in September 2001 where I was involved in different projects, and I am currently working in the Interactive Sonic Systems group on sound synthesis for the reacTable* project and on embedded devices.

For my work on computer music systems, there are three main points on which I want to focus, one is the concept of a computer music system and its definition, the second one is a description of systems in terms of programming language and a third one is the relation between using computer music systems and the task of programming, or more generally the usage and intuitiveness aspect of computer music systems.

1.2 Computer Music Systems

A computer music language is a programming language that is specialized in solving problems that occur in Computer Music. The level of specializations vary in different computer music languages, hence the border between a programming language, a computer specialised music language and computer music system is blurry. It is hard to tell the conceptual difference between a music/dsp library for a general purpose programming language, a specific computer music language and the graphical applications which reflect the same principle of computation. These aspects will be described later on, here I state that I basically want to include any kind of software that is used for producing computer music with a certain level of flexibility. I also try to focus on the common aspects of the systems in the hope to find some implementation patterns. Nevertheless, I define a computer music system as

Orchestra:

```
instr 1
asig oscil 10000, 440, 1
out asig
endin
```

Score:

```
f1 0 256 10 1 ; a sine wave function table
i1 0 1000 0
```

Figure 1.1: CSound sine tone

```
(definstrument simp ()
  (let* ((j 0))
    (run (loop for i from 0 below 44100 do
              (outa i (sin (* j 2.0 pi (/ frequency *srate*))))
            (incf j))))
  (with-sound () (simp)))
```

Figure 1.2: CLM sine tone

a system that is a self-contained software package which allows to flexibly handle digital sound data in a creative way and is targeted to musicians and composers.

1.3 Programming Languages

Independent from the implementation of a computer music system they might share some common properties with programming languages. Being able to describe systems in terms of programming language theory enables a broader view of the systems. My description of computer music systems (CMS) will focus on how well ideas can be expressed with the systems programming language paradigms and try to figure out which of the existing paradigms fit

Figure 1.3: Pure Data sine tone

```
{Out.ar(SinOsc.ar(440.,0,0.2))}.play
```

Figure 1.4: SuperCollider sine tone

best to the different problems, and try to define new paradigms specific to the domain where a clear solution is missing.

Figures 1.1,1.2, 1.4 and 1.3 show four examples of computer music systems, CLM [60] a system implemented in Common Lisp, and therefore a sort of LISP library, Csound [69], a custom built programming language implementing some concepts of descriptive programming languages, Pure Data [51], a graphical programming language, hard to capture with common programming language design concepts, and therefore very interesting as a research topic. The last example is written in the SuperCollider [46] language, a CMS based on a smalltalk like language.

1.4 Using and Programming

Human Computer Interaction (HCI) can take place on several different levels. For the task of the production of an artistic work our interest focuses on two main aspects of HCI, that is usefulness and intuitiveness.

Sometimes intuitiveness gets bound to graphical user interface metaphors,

but we rather want to look at it from a more general point of view, which means "intuitiveness" is not what the user interface looks like (be it graphical or textual), but how natural it is to express conceptual ideas within the software. This should be possible using some general concepts of the domain the software is working in, and giving examples how this can be expressed within each of the systems. The ability to adapt to a specific domain offers the possibility to include more domain knowledge into the system, hence making it more intuitive, but at the same time it bears the danger of forcing its user too much into a specific direction of thought.

Usefulness of a human computer interface denotes the degree to which the interface is useful in finishing a specific task. For a flexible programming environment usefulness is hard to measure, because we can't know in advance for which specific tasks the system will be used. An important aspect is that the system is reasonable complete in that most of the possible ideas can be expressed in some way.

In the next chapters I will try to take a look at existing computer music systems from different points of view and outline their implementations, starting with a historical review.

Chapter 2

Computer Music Systems

Review

In order to be able to get a concise presentation of the nature of techniques that are used in CMS we will mainly refer to already existing systems and how they solved a specific problem. For the reader not familiar with the history of computer music this chapter will give a short and fast overview. Additionally we classified the systems into a temporal-functional system that we found adapts very well and produces only few overlaps.

2.1 From Music I to GROOVE

The era of computer music started in 1957 when Max Mathews wrote the first software synthesis program called **Music I**. It ran on an IBM 704 computer at Bell laboratories where Mathews was working.

At that time programs were mainly written in assembler for performance reasons and because of the lack of real high level languages, and so was Music I, the first incarnation of a series of programs known today as Music-N

Mathews was going through iterations of updates on the Music I program, which eventually led to a version that was called **Music V**, written in the high level language Fortran this time.

Music V can be considered as the breakthrough of the line of programs referenced as Music-N. Mathews Book about Music V [23] is still one of the main reference works about the structure of computer music systems, and the Music V system produced and still produces systems that follow its basic principles. One could say that Music V defined the structure of Computer Music programs and influenced and formed the way we think about Computer Music, especially if we talk about software synthesis practice.

At the time when Music V was written, computers were not fast enough to calculate audio signals in real time, so Music V was a program that was used to calculate sound files in non-realtime. In the early 70ties, Max Mathews started another project called the **GROOVE** system, [44] the first system that was designed for realtime control of synthesizers.

Other important works from the early era include the **MUSICOMP** [36] system by Lejaren Hiller, author of the first published computer music work in 1958, the ILLIAC suite. This system was a composition system, and not a sound synthesis package.

The **MUSIGOL** system was a sound synthesis package based on the ALGOL language, one of the first high level languages that appeared during that time.[42]

2.2 Music-N Descendants

The Music series of programs where a success, and the fact that Mathews shared the code with other institutions together with the need to port the

code to the different computer architectures lead to several extended versions of Music-N

One line that came out of this process was the **Music4B** and **Music4BF** from Godfrey Windham and Hubert Howe. The F in Music 4BF stands for Fortran, which means that parts of that system were implemented in Fortran too.

Building up on Music 4B Berry Vercoe wrote a CMS for the IBM System/360 which he called **Music 360** in 1968, later on in 1974 a program for the PDP-11 **Music 11**. A direct follow up of Music 11 was CSound, coming in 1985, today maybe the best known and most used incarnation of a MUSIC-N system.

At Stanford yet another advanced incarnation of MusicV was developed, called MUS10, featuring an ALGOL like instrument language and enhanced set of unit generators.

Software wise the language of choice for high level performance programming in the late seventies, early eighties was “C”, and so several systems that were implemented in “C” appeared, like Paul Lansky’s **Cmix** program. Cmix is more a library than a computer music language, as Cmix is compiled and linked by a C compiler. Still, it has its own Instrument description language, called **MINC**, which is used to translate Cmix instruments into C source code.

Together with the book “Elements of Computer Music”, F. Richard Moore wrote a system he called **cmusic**. Cmusic can be seen as a reimplementation of Music V in C.

Another system widely in use today that came out of the Music V tradition is CLM[60], which stands for Common Lisp Music.

Although these are the more obvious successors of the Music-N languages,

all modern CMS share some of the ideas of Music-N, so that we can say that its principles are generally accepted.

As a counterpoint I want to mention a very interesting CMS, which probably fits into this section because it might be the only “non-Music V” system for sound generation available. This is the **Sawdust** system by Herbert Brun. The system computes waveforms based on strict rules, but these rules are not at all influenced by psychoacoustic or DSP theory, generating really new and never heard sounds, but being very hard to “control”.

2.3 Control Languages

Control Languages are computer music languages that don’t include the synthesis of sounds, but are used on a higher level for organizing and structuring how sound is handled in a CMS. The Music-N style score could be seen as a primitive control language. Nevertheless a score is only an explicit list of events with times and parameters, and as such doesn’t qualify as programming language. It is rather a descriptive language, we won’t include descriptive languages in this survey (such as Score languages, MIDI or OSC), because they mainly deal with structure, not with algorithms. Our concern is not how to define structure but how to generate it automatically, termed generative languages by Loy et.al.[38].

Music V supported a simple system that was using a routine called CONVT that could translate and combine instrument parameter values.

The already mentioned MUSICOMP system by Hiller was one of the first higher level score description systems, that implemented traditional harmonic rules. After the establishment of the Music-N paradigms, a logical step to take was to compute score files using algorithms written in (already exist-

ing) higher level languages, or designing languages that can express these algorithms.

One of these score languages was **SCORE** [64], generally a preprocessor for Music V score files which translated CPN (Common Practice Notation) to a score file, but this language was not able to generate a score automatically. Expanding on the idea of CPN notation the system PLA [61] was implemented as an extension to the SAIL (Stanford Artificial Intelligence Language) programming language and Lisp, making automatic score generation very flexible.

FORMES is a score generating system written in VLISP, an object oriented system for high level description of musical processes, developed at IRCAM.

Other score preprocessing languages appeared, like **CScore** and **Cybil** for CSound. With the availability of realtime software synthesizers in the late 70ties, focus started to shift over to realtime control languages, languages that were used to control synthesizers and had to react to realtime input from composers or players.

2.4 Realtime Control Systems, Sequencers

We already mentioned the GROOVE system, which controlled analog synthesizers by generating sampled function values as control values in real time on a digital computer. This allowed for algorithmic, although somewhat crude, control of analog synthesizers and interaction by a player.

A more elaborate language for realtime control was **PLAY**. PLAY could generate and manipulate control streams which could be individually clocked and sent to the synthesizers synthesis modules. PLAY was a dataflow lan-

guage, which means that the control it produces is constantly flowing, it didn't have the notion of instantaneous events. Several principles in music are event based though.

4CED [2] was a control language for the 4C synthesizer at IRCAM and its score generating system was based on event processing. This means that instead of having constant dataflows, the control changes get triggered by events, which in turn can trigger other events or phrases of scores.

Max Mathews **RTSKED** [45] was another event based system which had some notion of multitasking built-in.

A descendent of RTSKED is the **Music 500** [52] system which was replacing the traditional score file by a system based on the "trigger" and "waitf" idea of Mathews.

Flavours Band [25] is another LISP based system for realtime control, which was built on the notion of phrase processors that can be manipulated and applied to phrases and has influenced systems like Steven Travis Pope's **MODE**.

Other early systems that can be mentioned in this domain are **MOXIE** [12] and **FMX**, all reflecting the state of the art of realtime CMS at that time.

A language wise very interesting approach is the **ARCTIC**[18] system by Roger Dannenberg. ARCTIC is functional language with descriptive elements. The main semantic concept consists of prototypes for events. These events, once instantiated can trigger other events or produce output functions. Time was an explicit value in ARCTIC. The event propagation was similar to that of 4CED.

Because of the constant hardware improvements, only a few control languages of that time survived the platform they were written for. In the mid

80ties Miller Puckette was working on a program to control the newly developed 4X machine at IRCAM, his program was called **MAX** [54] (after Max Mathews) and it was written for an Apple Macintosh computer.

Several coincidences lead to the fact that MAX survived, one is surely the upcoming market for personal computers like the Macintosh and the establishment of the MIDI protocol, which started in the mid eighties. Max is an event based system, just as RTSKED or Flavours Band. It had one novelty and that was its graphical representation of the language statements. Operation could be patched together just like in the representation everyone knew from the Music V orchestra explanations. Max communicated with the 4X via MIDI, which made it also useable for any other commercial synthesizer, and probably not as useful for computer music. MAX got also used as a control language for the following development of the IRCAM Signal Processing Workstation (ISPW) [21].

The popularity of mainstream synthesizers, that led to the definition of the MIDI standard in 1983, also led to a set of programs for controlling these devices. Due to the limited parameter space of the MIDI protocol these control programs, called sequencers, were basically not more than a graphical user interface to a stripped down version of Music-N scores.

Although problematic, the separation of control and synthesis for real-time systems stayed unavoidable until the mid 90ties, when general purpose computers started to be able to take over the task of dedicated hardware.

2.5 General Purpose High Level Languages

Several system have been implemented in general purpose languages, which were not primarily designed for computer music. There are several languages

which have been chosen for this task, the most important ones are probably Smalltalk and Lisp, both supposed to be representatives of two different styles of programming, namely object oriented and functional. There are only few languages in common use that only implement one of the identifiable programming paradigms. There might be as many programming paradigms as there are problems to solve, maybe one of the future goals of a CMS is to find the programming paradigm that fits best to the problems in the domain.

Not a high-level language in its modern definition the **Formula** system [4] used a Forth interpreter as its implementation language.

The **MODE** (Musical Object Development Environment) [49] is a system written in Smalltalk which supports structured composition and flexible graphical editing of high and low level musical objects. It includes a score description language called **SmOke**.

Another Smalltalk based system is **Kyma** [58], a system that depends on the separation of synthesis engine on a DSP and the control interface, which, in Kyma's case is mainly graphical.

Currently the widest used system based on a smalltalk like language is probably **SuperCollider** [46], which actually went back in concept to the separation of synthesis and control language. The SuperCollider synthesis engine can be controlled by other means too, for example Python or Q[26].

Lisp systems are several, starting from already mentioned CLM, over **Patchwork** [39], **OpenMusic** [6] and Roger Dannenberg's **Nyquist** [15], a language evolved from ARCTIC, based on xisp. Lisp itself was pretty successful and accepted by composers, it has a clear syntax, is interpreted and therefore highly interactive. The handling of lists of dynamically allocated data lends itself directly to the idea of writing a score, which then can be manipulated by the language in one environment. Lisp syntax is really easy

conceptually, but in the long term it might be hard to read.

Another example of an application of functional language to computer music is the **Haskore** [29] system, written in Haskell, a modern functional language.

In general it can be said that the most important feature of the successful languages in this domain share one common principle, which is interactivity. This topic will be touched later.

2.6 Realtime DSP Languages

Soon after computers were fast enough to do signal processing in realtime, systems for sound synthesis were proliferating. Several of the surviving synthesis programs of the post Music V era started to work in realtime, interestingly with only a few adjustments. Software Sound synthesis in the style of Csound, cmusic and cmix had their own evolution during the years of expensive and dedicated computer music workstations. The time that it took to render a csound score to disk got smaller and smaller from year to year, until it was shorter than the actual piece.

An interesting adaption of the Music N orchestra file for realtime interaction is the **M** orchestra language [53] of the Music 500 system, running on a special purpose array processor, though.

Besides the Music V style languages, another survivor to the era of signal processing on general purpose computers was Max, and specifically its successors Pure Data, jMax and MAX/MSP.

Having the whole system running on one computer facilitated several aspects of the control problem, but it didn't let it go away. Obviously the problem of controlling sound processing and synthesis specifically in realtime

is not a problem of the synthesis/control separation but lies deep within the algorithms themselves [31].

The nineties saw other trends in computer technology showing up, one of which is the Internet. In order to be able to handle bandwidth problems the Music V paradigm got yet another modern incarnation called **SAOL** (Structured Audio Orchestra Language) with its score language **SASL** [59]. SAOL is a MPEG-4 standard, but it didn't get widely adopted, maybe because of the lack of an efficient interpreter.

Another field that has opened with the availability of fast desktop computers are libraries and frameworks that can be used to build CMS. They cover different areas, from simple sound processing libraries to complete cross-platform solutions. Systems that should be mentioned here are the Synthesis Toolkit (STK) [13] and the sndobj [37] library which implement signal processing or instrument algorithms and the CLAM[5] framework, which offers everything from signal processing, scheduling, graphical user interface, sound hardware access up to a whole MetaModel of music computation [3].

2.7 Current Developments

Some of the systems mentioned above are still heavily in use and evolving. Other systems are very recent and it has yet to be seen if they will be of the same importance as some of the systems we have seen so far.

As quick wrapup, I want to mention some of these systems. First there are more Max style implementations, **Open Sound World** [1] can be considered as one of these. It tries to overcome several shortcomings of the (already 20 year old) Max paradigms, fighting against a strong user-base of Max and Pure Data.

Other interesting additions to the Max paradigm are graphic rendering libraries. This way the Max program also got interest from visual artists.

A new approach on how to handle the problems in computer music is being tried by **Chuck** [70], which introduces the concept of a “strongly timed language”, referring to its sample synchronous scheduler, and the expression of “on-the-fly” programming, a technique used in order to improvise computer music, also known as live-patching, just-in-time programming, and live-coding.

The **CLAM** [5] framework is on its way of setting a new standard with higher level datatypes for spectral processing and in the rather new field of music information retrieval. CLAM is also seen as a replacement for traditional scientific tools such as Matlab.

The **Marsyas** [67] system is yet another analysis/synthesis library with a specialty on music information retrieval.

Other recent systems are based on functional programming (Q-lang) [26] and **Chronic** [9] or the research system **Varese**, based on the Lisp dialect Scheme [27].

Java also has its CMS in **JSyn** [10] and **JMusic** [65], and for music description the **JMSL** (Java Music Specification Language), successor of **HSML** the Hierarchical Music Specification Language.

Several systems are not as much concerned about programmability, they rather implement system based on the more traditional concept of modular synthesizer/sequencer combination, like **AudioMulch** [8]. or Bidule.

Due to the proliferation of computer music software the ways how composers work with computers have definitely changed. Nevertheless, CMS are still looked for, especially for interactive art and live performances, as in most of these cases the system plays a key role both in aesthetics and in the

technical effort that is needed for its realization.

Looking at the systems that are most widely used today it seems that there is still room left to improve and make computer music better accessible to musicians.

2.8 Conclusion

It is difficult to tell the future impact of specific CMS implementations, to round up this chapter I would like to talk about some points of the described systems which, in my opinion, influenced their acceptance.

With the plethora of CMS that were written until today it is clear that the acceptance of a system can't be the only measure of its quality. In fact, some systems disappeared or didn't evolve in what they were supposed to be because of external influences that are not related to the system itself.

Starting with Music-N systems, as can be seen by today's implementations and the practice of computer music education, the Unit Generator concept, initially drawn from the workings of analog synthesizers, has become a sort of ground truth in digital signal processing for music.

It is astonishing, and at the same time understandable that systems based on higher level languages such as Lisp or Smalltalk became popular at the same time as graphical patching. It seems that programming by patching makes certain tasks easy, but then at the end some ideas are just a lot easier expressible in a standard programming language. This might indicate that the graphical patching still has its room to improve or that expressing algorithms graphically is and will be very hard.

We described several systems that were built upon general purpose interpreted languages, and it seems that using a well established language helps

a lot during the development. Not all languages offer the needed robustness regarding the tight timing constraints that exist in interactive computer music applications, so the speed of the language interpreter is still one of the main criteria. Another point in favor of using a general purpose language is the complexity of musical information on the control level [57], a problem that is still not solved and is probably only solvable for distinct cases.

Considering the user friendliness of languages, it is said that scripting languages are easier to learn and handle. Music making, to a considerable part, is a very experimental activity, especially if someone wants to explore the sound possibilities that computer music offers.

If a language is not general purpose it seems to be even more important to have a facility to extend the language. The computer music communities contribution to systems like CSound or Max/Pd to name two domain specific languages seems to be a key to their success and sustainability.

Chapter 3

Outline of Computer Music System Concepts

As has been shown in the last chapter, a considerable number of software systems are being and have been written for computer music. The design and the implementation of such a variety had its specific need for every system, which might be a change of hardware (as happened in the early days), change of operating systems through time, advances in language research, new ideas and paradigms, new insights in human computer interaction, or simple just the sign of the times, which get reflected in the systems that people develop and use.

This chapter will try to extract the key ideas that are used in the systems in order to ask what a modern computer music system would consist of. We will partially reference to the systems mentioned in the previous chapter, but in this chapter the conceptual ideas will be outlined. Our main reference will be Music-N, as it has anticipated several of the crucial points.

Some concepts that will be outlined in this chapter have been added by the author in order to give a complete picture of the possible choices when

Figure 3.1: A unit generator diagram

designing a CMS.

3.1 General Concepts

3.1.1 The UnitGenerator

“There are certain strains of elements of our musical beings that seem right because they help us solve the problems that we need to solve, such as, for instance, the unit generator” - Gareth Loy

Probably the most influential idea introduced by Mathews was the concept of the unit generator (UG). The idea of the UG is derived from analog synthesis, where modules such as oscillators, LFO (low frequency oscillators), envelope generators and filters get plugged together in order to realize a specific sound generation algorithm. The data paths through which these modules communicate with each other are driven by voltage signals. The fact that all elements deliver the same kind of signal makes the construction of new algorithms very flexible in analog synthesizers. This idea was

directly mapped to the digital domain, the signals sampled and the modules implemented in software. The implementation of UGs in software is not straightforward though. Digital computation takes time, and the computation of one sample for every channel of audio at a rate of 44100 was quite a task at the beginning of computer music and we still want to minimize the time spent computing, always looking for a good balance between performance and quality.

Normally one looks at a unit generator as a single fundamental, non divide-able process, an implementation of a basic calculation primitive. This is used in order to implement higher level algorithms. The code of each unit generator can run for a specific time, “consuming” and “generating” audio data. After that a scheduler has to decide which unit generator has to be run next. If the time that a unit generator has run is shorter than its life span (in Music N the live span would be a note), then the UG has to remember its state for the next run.

Therefore, in programming language terms the unit generator can be looked at from different points of view.

First, it is similar to a thread, with its state, input and output pipes. The thread gets started by an instantiation of an instrument, it waits for its input data to be ready and based on this it gets scheduled automatically, being called to calculate the next n values.

In terms of functional programming, the unit generator is captured by the concept of a closure, a function that preserves its environment and state. In C++ Functors implement the closure concept loosely.

It is possibly easiest to describe a UG in object oriented terms. Although the generator has only one non trivial function (or method) it is important to be able to access and change other properties of the generator. In the

functional model these properties can only be set through passing parameters to the UG's main function. When modelling a unit generator as an object its state can be changed asynchronously (while running), an important property for being able to interact in realtime with the system, and a good example how data locality helps in organizing the parameter space.

In general the UG properties should also be changeable by other UG signals, which would favor a combined functional (e.g parameters get passed to the function) and object oriented approach. Polymorphism or default arguments are a must for this to work.

3.1.2 Data Centered Signal Processing

Although not widely used in computer music systems, an important concept that contrasts with the Music V approach is the data driven approach, mainly used in scientific computation and mathematical languages such as MATLAB [32], Octave [22], LastWave [7], the Python numarray [47] extension or the Template Numerical Toolkit (TNT) [50].

These languages define array or matrix types as their main data types. Types are equivalent to objects, which means that they are data containers with access and manipulation methods. The methods implement the different mathematical operation on the data. Also, in these systems, operators can be used directly on arrays of data, leaving space for optimization (of the kind we will see below) as well as being easily understandable and intuitive to read.

The data can always be accessed directly, an important feature for the flexibility of the systems.

Our C++ library Toluene is a research system based on the C++ Template Numerical Toolkit and implements a Wave class, which is a TNT array

```
#include <wave.h>
#include <iostream>

int main(int argc, char** argv)
{
    Wave a(0,9,1);
    Wave b(0,9,1);
    cout << a + b << endl;
    cout << a*3.141 << endl;
}
```

Figure 3.2: Code for adding 2 Wave's in Toluene

enhanced with some MATLAB like functionality. Figure 3.1.2 shows a small but complete program in toluene to add two arrays of numbers.

These systems do not offer classical CMS features such as automatic scheduling, but their data representation is very general and compact, consisting mainly of arrays and matrices of numbers. This way signal processing algorithms can be easily implemented and because of the compatibility of its data types reuseability is guaranteed. The functions and operators on the data correspond to the UG's of Music N.

In the computer music domain these tools are mainly used for the development of signal processing algorithms, as they do not lend themselves easily to the task of interactive or realtime sound generation, and the interpreted systems (MatLab, Octave, LastWave and numarray) are too slow for efficient realtime computation.

The TNT based toluene might be a solution that offers both, flexibility and speed.

```
1 INS 0 1 ;
2 OSC P5 P6 B2 F1 P30 ;
3 OSC B2 P7 B2 F2 P29 ;
4 OUT B2 B1 ;
5 END ;
6 GEN 0 1 1 0 0 .99 20 .99 491 0 511 ;
7 GEN 0 1 2 0 0 .99 205 -.99 306 -.99 461 0 511 ;
8 NOT 0 1 2 1000 0.0128 6.70 ;
9 NOT 2 1 1 1000 0.0256 8.44 ;
10 TER 3 ;
```

Figure 3.3: example Music V orchestra and score

3.1.3 The Score

While the unit generator modeled the analog synthesizer circuitry with its voltage levels as data, the main responsibility of the score is to handle timed events, on an analog synthesizer this corresponds to the human interaction like pressing keys and the trigger functions of the analog sequencer.

Besides the generation of lookup tables (the GEN entries in Figure 3.3, line 6 and 7) a score consists of timing information, instrument information and parameters for the instrument. It is a static data description language where each line specifies a record.

Generation of sound output is triggered by the NOT entries (Figure 3.3). The first parameter denotes time, the second one duration, the rest is passed to the instrument as parameters. Several NOT entries can be started at the same time or overlap.

The Music-N score language was soon found to be too limited for several tasks. First it is lacking verbosity, parameters can not be omitted and there is no support for default values. But more limiting than that, it doesn't allow for the expression of algorithms.

In general concept behind the score is still valid, if we look at it as the

output, an interim representation, of the dataflow between a controller or a computer music algorithm and the synthesizer. A method for realtime scheduling and dispatching of the score of a CMS is described by Dannenberg [16].

3.1.4 Instrument Description and Syntax

The orchestra files describe the instruments that can be used by the score file. The instruments consist of unit generators that are plugged together (see Figure 3.1). We can distinguish several different syntactical solutions how unit generators are plugged together. The resulting semantic tree is the same, but the way UGs are connected together make different scheduling practices more natural.

- MUSIC-V: The UGs can take their signals from a set of predefined audio busses (B1,B2 etc) and write back to them. In this case the user has to take care not to overwrite a signal that is used by another UG later in the same instrument.
- CSound lets you define variables and the buffer assignment is automatic, a flexible version of the Music V principle. Connection types are described by the first letter of the variable names. See below for a description of k-rate and a-rate connections.
- Another “patching Syntax” is used by SuperCollider. UGs are objects that are passed to the “ar” or “kr” method of other UGs. This defines the semantic tree as well as the types of connections between its nodes.

```
Out.ar(SinOsc.ar(220,0,0.1))
```

Supercollider lets you also assign subtrees to variables which avoids deep nested parenthesis constructs and offers operators (+,-,*,/) for these common UG's.

- In a functional language such as Nyquist, UGs are functions (closures) that get passed to other UGs as arguments.
- A syntax mostly used in graphical languages is to connect objects by explicit connect commands. Doing this in a textual language is difficult, as it involves the assignment of names to the UG's, in order to connect them later. The example from a Pd patch uses object indices (starting with 0) in order to reference to the correct objects.

```
#N canvas 0 0 450 300 10;  
#X obj 61 48 osc~ 220;  
#X obj 61 71 dac~ 1;  
#X connect 0 0 1 0;
```

- ChuckK uses a single operator in order to connect unit generators together *impulsei => biquadf => dac;*. This is syntactically not as powerful as other approaches, but it enhances the understandability of the code to some degree. The ChuckK operator works as a reverse assignment operator.

The unit generators are run one after the other as defined in the orchestra file. For Music N the management of the sound buses is explicit, which means that care has to be taken in order not to destroy or change the contents of one of the instruments buses ahead of time. Each time an instrument gets started the scheduler runs each unit generator in turn, the generators read their input parameters and data and write to their output busses.

Looking at the orchestra file (Figure 3.3 line 1 to 5) and comparing it with its graphical representation we can also see why graphical applications have been so successful. The Music-N notation of instruments is cumbersome although it has been improved over the years, whereas the graphical representation shows clearly what is going on. The semantics for both approaches are the same.

3.1.5 Polyphony

Music N is not a realtime language but a batch processing language, therefore the instrument invocations can be calculated one after another, making polyphonic scores easy by reusing the same instance of an instrument for each voice and just resetting its state.

In realtime systems this method does not work anymore, so each instrument defined in the orchestra is not automatically a data object, but only a template for creating voices of the instrument. In a realtime language each invocation of an instrument therefore creates the instrument and releases it after its usage.

In a realtime context updating of parameters gets more complicated, because if we want to change the behavior of a voice in realtime it is not obvious which voice of the instrument has to be changed.

This is generally solved by giving the possibility of assigning explicit names to voices or by automatically assigning unique numbers to them.

The problem is even more unclear in a graphical representation. Is the representation the template or an instance of the voice. As one of the advantages of the graphical representation is the possibility of direct interaction into a running instrument, it is not clear how to interact if several instances of the same instrument are running.

The problem of how to handle polyphony in the light of realtime parameter updates is still open.

3.2 Setup and Control

As we already saw, the score concept of Music V has proved to be too limited for the needs of computer music. In the last chapter we also introduced computer music systems that are used for control. This section deals with this layer. Generally, what is needed is a way to specify events and parameter changes for the instruments as well as a layer that makes it possible to map events that come from the outside (keyboard, mouse or any other controller) in a sensible way to our instrument parameters.

It has to be added that the concept of separation between instrument and control introduced by Music-N systems is not unambiguous. If we design a control layer for musical signal processing we are already defining an abstraction of the synthesis algorithms (a part of the system that should stay as open as possible). It would be ideal if the abstraction of what to control can be defined within the system.

Even more flexibility is achieved with the dynamic or algorithmic creation of instruments, instead of defining them statically. The graphical metaphor is not so clear anymore in this case, the orchestra language becomes a meta instrument language, which can deliver hundreds of different instruments.

Another domain of control is “dynamic patching” [43] between UG’s, which means the possibility not only to generate but also to change instruments algorithmically from the control layer.

3.2.1 Score Generation

Trying to move a layer beyond the static score description of Music-N, the question is how the score should be generated, be it realtime or non-realtime. As described in the last chapter, early systems used a twofold approach, where a musical event got expressed by a score statement, and finer grained control was built into the orchestra language.

The question within traditional Music V system is where to put the algorithm, into the orchestra or the score. Again a question of abstraction of the synthesis algorithms into some control variables that can be changed.

A common approach to the problem of static score are preprocessors. These are Modules that generate a score from a higher level score description language. Yet another approach is to calculate the score using a general programming language. In any case, an advantage of score generation is the possibility to “see into the future” and opens up a wide field of algorithms which are not possible with realtime processing.

3.2.2 Event Generation and Processing

The programmed approach to score generation is rather straight forward and can be implemented in any general purpose language. Several schemes have been proposed about how to handle high level musical information, but we think that this part should be left open to the user of the CMS.

Realtime control is quite different as it depends on events in time where the information has to be processed and a “realtime score” has to be written immediately. Analogous to the implementation of common user interface systems, events are handled in event callbacks, which in turn trigger some actions.

For realtime score generation the system waits for events, and processes them as soon as they enter. This concept for realtime can also be applied to non realtime, providing a layer between the score and the synthesis engine. In this case the order of execution is Score -> Events -> Orchestra.

This concept can also be looked at as a flexible extension of the Music V CONVT routine.

Several of the realtime event processing systems define some notion of event-processors, entities that can receive events, perform calculations on them, and send new events. The newly generated events can either be sent immediately or scheduled for a later time.

After passing through all the event processors, the result of the transformations in time and data normally updates some parameters of a signal processing algorithm.

The event passing and processing principle seems to be so natural to the task of controlling computer music systems, that Dannenberg when describing Aura has to admit “.. that we had come quite close to reinventing MAX semantics.”, which in turn are just another implementation of the concept introduced by 4CED and RTSKED.

3.2.3 Orchestra Generation

The Music N orchestra language is a declarative, static language. Newer systems like Supercollider or ChuckK offer a language to construct instruments through programming. This is a very powerful concept, as it allows to construct specialized small instruments instead of creating one big instrument that covers every aspect through parameter changes. This approach might be less intuitive and harder to debug, though.

3.3 Performance Optimization

One of the main aspects and difficulties when implementing a CMS is the performance aspect. An audio signal carries a lot of data and computing this data can be expensive. From the very start strategies have been designed in order to keep the computation cost low. In this section I will outline some of these strategies.

3.3.1 Performance Bottlenecks

First we are going to try to analyze performance bottlenecks. The structure of modern general purpose processors and their capabilities can lead to bottlenecks in the following cases:

- **Computation of complex mathematical functions.** Higher mathematical functions like sine or cosine form the basis of digital signal processing. Unfortunately these functions are not built-in into the processor, so in order to calculate them an approximation algorithm has to be carried out for every sample. This is expensive in terms of computing power.
- **1st level cache and memory transfers.** The huge amount of audio data that has to be processed, can lead to a serious performance degradation when the memory needed during the main loop of the instrument does not fit into the processors cache, and the data therefore has to be fetched upon every iteration from the main memory.
- **Scheduling and function call overhead.** Some of the unit generators do simple tasks, like addition. For these operations calling the UG function and loading the state data into registers takes more time

than the actual computation. Also the usage of registers in this case is not optimal. Scheduling overhead is also the main obstacle to fast interpreters (see Appendix A for a detailed description of the problem).

Some general purpose optimization techniques can be applied to audio software, some examples of these techniques are:

- Loop unrolling: Sometimes the overhead of a test and branch operation can be avoided if we already know that the operations in our loop will be compiled several times.
- SIMD (Single Instruction Multiple Data) operations are implemented in most modern general purpose processors. Using these instruction gives a gain in performance, but generality and portability is lost.
- Register allocation of variables. Speed can be gained by fitting the variables needed in a computation loop into registers. In this case they do not have to be fetched from memory.

3.3.2 Signal and Control Rate

One solution to the performance problem was the introduction of signal and control rate calculations. This means that systems such as Csound run at two different clocks, one for sample by sample calculations and another one for calculations that can be done less frequently.

This way part of the values that steer UGs don't have to be loaded for each sample and can be kept inside a register in the inner loop of a unit generator.

Control rate signals are mainly used for amplitude changes, low frequency oscillators and similar unit generators. The ratio between control rate and signal rate can normally be adapted.

In terms of functionality the distinction between control and signal rate do not add new features. The user itself has to take care if she wants to use control or signal rate for a certain calculation. Detecting automatically if the calculation should be control or signal rate would be an extension to the idea, there exists no system which has implemented this idea though.

3.3.3 Control Signals versus Events

One way to control instruments is by changing control signals. Sometimes this is still an overhead, and a loss in flexibility because the parameter in question might be constant during a long part of the computation and have rapid changes during others. In these situations it is difficult to adjust the global control rate as it might be too fast for some part and too slow for others.

Realtime control systems are therefore mostly implemented on an event based model, also avoiding having to decide on a control rate that fits. Nevertheless, even with event based systems the resolution that can be attained with control messages is limited in most cases.

3.3.4 Table Lookup

In order to overcome the performance problems of mathematical operations tables were used since the beginning to make these calculations faster. The quality of the mathematical operation depends apart from other influences like the range of the function output on the size of the table. For sine oscillators the function output is bounded, also in its derivatives which allows us to calculate the worst signal to noise ratio that the table lookup will introduce. First, we assume that the biggest deviation will be at the steepest part of the signal (around the 0 point for a sine table). This deviation is smaller than $\sin(2 * \pi / 1024)$, our Noise to Signal ratio should be -96 dB (16

bit resolution) $1.525878e-05$, from $SNR = \sin(2 * \pi/N)$ we can extract N (where NSR is $1/SNR$).

$$N = 2 * \pi / \text{invsin}(NSR) = 7186.8266$$

Standard tables are powers of 2, so our sine table should have a size of 8192 in order to hold a sine tone. Note that this is a very pessimistic estimate, as generally through a phase shift of π/N we can half the maximum expected error. The error we calculate is the highest possible step between two consecutive samples. The real error is only half of that, when we round instead of truncate, but we introduce a phase error, which should be neglectable. The tablesize/calculation cost can be balanced by introducing linear or cubic interpolation. Other functions are not as easily representable by tables, especially traditional analog synthesizer generators like square or saw wave suffer aliasing. For speed reasons wavetables can be pre-calculated by interpolation or other techniques [63].

For real world samples interpolation in realtime is needed, as they are generally too long to be held in memory in a resampled version.

3.3.5 Block Computation

Most of the systems use block computation for performance reasons. The different advantages of block computations can be expressed as following:

- loop unrolling
- SIMD instructions
- reduction of function call overhead
- rate reduction of control updates

```
float scale = 0.4;
for (i=0;i<16;i++)
    *out++ = *in1++ * scale;

float scale = 0.4;
for (i=0;i<4;i++) {
    a1 = *in1++;
    a2 = *in1++;
    a3 = *in1++;
    a4 = *in1++;
    *out++ = a1*scale;
    *out++ = a2*scale;
    *out++ = a3*scale;
    *out++ = a4*scale;
}
```

Figure 3.4: example of low level loop unrolling technique

In order to use all of these tuning possibilities the blocksize has to be a multiple of a basic block. SIMD instructions for example might work on 4 values at the same time, so the final block size has to be at least 4 or a multiple thereof.

Also loop unrolling techniques only work with known block sizes. (see Figure 3.3.5). Loop unrolling might look tedious, but it generally pays off and it is portable (e.g. doesn't depend on the loop-unrolling facilities of the compiler). In C clever macros can help with the task, in C++ template meta programming might be used to implement such constructs [68].

The drawback of using block calculations is the limited flexibility in expressing algorithms. Several of the algorithms depend on direct access to samples of samples computed in the past (IIR filters). It is hard to express these algorithms in terms of UGs that work on a block of samples only.

Additionally the timing resolution gets limited through the usage of block computations. In general system block sizes are between 16 and 64 samples, which yields a resolution between 0.726 ms and 1.451 ms. For musical, singular events this time resolution is generally enough.

Some algorithms like signal feedback sometimes need more resolution.

3.4 Algorithm Related Concepts

An interesting goal is to define a base set of UGs that suffice for general computer music tasks. One might encounter that these are not that much, but several of them are closely related to specific algorithms, so in general it is hard to define a language consisting of general UGs that fits all tasks. This is still one of the main problems of computer music systems, and most of them suffer the problem that they have to be extended outside the system with some custom written C or C++ code in order to run fast enough. With our work we tried to address the problem by allowing lowlevel code to be used in interpreted languages (see article in appendix A).

3.4.1 Wavetables

We have already described the principle of table lookup for the implementation of complex mathematical functions. The same technique can be generalized for any waveform. The signal to noise ratio is normally low for smooth functions with small derivatives. As a generalization of table lookup oscillator wavetable synthesis is implemented in the same manner. Other uses for wavetables are granular and sampling synthesis. In Music V system wavetables are filled with commands in the score.

3.4.2 Delay and Delaylines

An important role in computer music is played by delays. Delays are the basic building blocks of filters, are needed for reverberation and play an important role in physical modelling. It therefore pays off to think about the effective implementation of delays. A naive approach might be to write an UG that stores a certain amount of the signal and sends it out after a certain delay, specified by one of its parameters. Thinking twice this is not the most flexible and fastest solution.

Generally we can gain by splitting the task of delaying into two UGs. One that is implementing a delayline writer, and another one that is reading from the delayline. This way it is possible to use more than one UG to read the delayline, or to implement different algorithms to control the delay length, have interpolating and non-interpolating versions.

The implementation of a single delay is still possible. The most difficult part is how to connect a delayline with its respective reader syntactically. In the MAX paradigm this is done through names, which has its drawbacks in having to find unambiguous names.

3.4.3 Feedback

Delayline UGs with their associated readers are straightforward to implement. Care has to be taken to make a connection in the DSP graph between the delayline and the delay reader, putting the delayline as an input to all its readers. Otherwise the order could get messed up and a delay beyond the blocksize of the respective scheduler cycle would not be possible.

The implementation of delaylines with feedback is more complicated, and also the execution order of the delayline UG and the delay read UG change.

Figure 3.5: delayline and delay reader - single delay UG

This means that the feedback loop has a minimal delay of the blocksize of the scheduler, in the extremest case 1 sample. This also means that the connection between the delayline and the delay reader is “weaker” than any connection that leads to an input of the delay reader to the delayline.

3.4.4 Granular Synthesis

Granular synthesis is especially demanding with regards to CMS concepts, as it needs a high level of dynamic instantiation with a exact time granularity and speed. Most of the systems therefor integrate granular synthesis as a separate UG. Considering the fact that the principles of granular synthesis are not significantly more complex than other standard synthesis techniques the implementation of granular synthesis only using the standard UG’s is a good test for the completeness of a certain approach.

3.5 Implementation Details

We have described the building blocks of computer music systems, another important aspect that is still missing is how to put these blocks together. There are several ways to do this and we will try to take a look at some of the implementation details of software synthesis systems.

3.5.1 Static Scheduling

In the Music-N languages used explicit scheduling. Modern systems try to take away this responsibility from the user and do the scheduling automatically. We will describe two basic types of static scheduling mechanisms, source to sink and source callbacks and discuss their advantages and disadvantages.

Explicit Function Calls

In this scheme the scheduling is handled directly by nested function calls. An example of an implementation is STK, where the routine that calculates the signal of every UG is called `tick()`. In STK the C++ function call resolving takes care of scheduling. If we want to connect a source to several sinks, the result of the `tick()` function of the source has to be stored in a temporal variable. The single sample calculation scheme used by STK makes this very easy, but the performance of the system is not optimized.

Tree Search

The static scheduling is the fastest way of scheduling during runtime. The scheduling algorithms are fast enough to recalculate the scheduling chain on the fly in most (but not all !!) situations.

```

#include <stk/RtWvOut.h>
#include <stk/Noise.h>
#include <stk/BiQuad.h>

int main() {

// Instantiate the ugens we need for calculation

RtWvOut dac(1);
Noise noise;
BiQuad biquad;
biquad.setResonance( 440.0, 0.98, true );

// run the engine

while (1)
    dac.tick(biquad.tick(noise.tick()));

}

```

Figure 3.6: A filtered noise example with STK

Figure 3.7: DSP graph of a modified Karplus strong resonator

When determining the scheduling we have to traverse a directed graph, make sure that the calculations of all inputs of each UG are scheduled before the corresponding UG, and detect feedback loops and delay lines and sort accordingly. A similar problem to the delayline exists for reading and writing into tables.

In order to determine the order of UG invocations we can apply graph search algorithms like depth first or breath first search.

Assuming that we have a DSP graph G (see figure 3.7), the algorithm for determining the scheduling would be the following:

We assume that we can find the set of incoming signals for each ugen.

```
R ... list of scheduled vertices
S ... set of sound sinks

resolve(UG u)
  if (u in R) error, feedback loop
  for each input i of u do
    resolve(i)
  add(R,u)

schedule(S)
  for each s in S do
    resolve(s)
  return R
```

This algorithm does not take the delayline problem into account, and just signals an error when a feedback is detected.

3.5.2 Dynamic Scheduling

Dynamic Scheduling is a bit slower during runtime, but it has the advantage that it produces a constant load, no matter if the UG graph is changed during

```
audio.start()

-- Setup the computation chain

o=Out(Sine(Add(250,Mult(1000,Sine(100))))))

-- Produce 1 second of sound

play(o,1000)
```

Figure 3.8: function call implementation in ALUA

execution. There are two general approaches to dynamic scheduling.

Function Call Based Scheduling

In this scheme each UG calls the functions that generate the input samples it needs for calculation. In order to be able to do this, the inputs of the functions have to be registered with the functions. The registration can be handled in different ways. Figure 3.8 shows an implementation of the concept using closures. Here, `Sine()`, `Add()`, `Mult()` are function constructors which automatically setup the DSP chain. The algorithm implements a frequency modulation function.

The difference between this scheduling strategy and the static scheduling above can be seen by the call to the `play()` function.

The nested function calls generate the graph, the `play()` function calls it and the scheduling is done from within the closures by calling the connected functions. Recursion detection can be implemented by counting the number of function entry and exits.

Data Trigger Based Scheduling

Another approach to dynamic scheduling would be scheduling triggered by messages. Several systems [73, 51, 17] use message passing on the event level for their calculations. The same system might be employed for signal calculations. The elegance in this solution would be to “unify” the paradigms of control and signal processing, where signal processing would just be an instance of event processing, with events flowing constantly. This would also make it easy to “turn off” parts of the calculations if they are not needed at a certain point.

A point of dispute in systems that use data passing for scheduling is when to schedule. There are several scenarios which can be taken into account.

UG has one input only

This is the trivial case. If the unit generator takes the data that it got sent, calculates the result and passes it on. Triggering further calculations.

UG has more than one input

In this case the question is when to trigger the calculation. There are three approaches which might be distinguished.

1. The calculation takes place when all data has arrived.

This approach seems to be the most natural one in the light of synchronous signal processing. The implementation of the scheme would be for each UG to check if the data slots are full (at each message it receives), set them to empty and calculate the result, which is then passed to the next UG. Another implementation detail would be to send the data with time information and trigger the calculation as soon as all input data has the same time tag.

2. The calculation takes place if the first input data is received.

This method is implemented in the MAX languages and adds more flexibility to the scheduling. For event processing this makes sense because this way default computation can take place (like adding a constant). Maybe this flexibility is not needed for streamed data, like sound.

3. Calculation upon every message.

This might make sense for event calculations (e.g. updates of all structures not depending on a specific event). Using this system for signal calculation does not make sense.

In general for the message passing scheme the connections go from source to sink. For data triggered scheduling the best solution would be to check every data input point and flag it when data has arrived or when no other signal object is connected. If all inputs are flagged, calculate the result.

3.5.3 DSP Memory Management

It is desirable that the CMS is as dynamic as possible, which means that care has to be taken about the resources it consumes. This is especially true for the allocation of the signal vectors the system is using. Because of performance reasons the memory footprint should be small, in this section I will try to discuss some strategies for memory optimization.

When the data management of the UG is handled from the outside, care has to be taken in which context the UG is run, depending on the access permissions to the input and output buffers.

Typical setups include:

- read and write buffer are independent. This means that the read buffer is valid during the whole computation, making it unnecessary to read

the values into temporal variables before writing to the output buffer.

- The read and write buffer might be the same. This means the UG has only access to input values where it hasn't written an output value yet.
- The output buffer is a bus, in this case the UG has to add the result to the output.

VST (Virtual Studio Technology) by Steinberg handles output buffers in two different ways, either as empty buffers, that get samples assigned, or as busses. A VST plugin (again, some sort of UG) can implement different routines for both cases.

We leave strategies for memory allocation for a future point of investigation, but we want to resume some guidelines for building special memory management systems for signal data.

1. Keep the signal memory localized, e.g. preallocate it and reuse the preallocated part.
2. Keep the signal memory as small as possible, this way we can assure to keep it in the processors cache.
3. reuse as much of the memory as possible.

3.6 Higher Level Concepts

3.6.1 Hierarchical Structure

We have been talking about UG, instruments and the implementation of signal processing algorithms. This abstraction has partly historical reasons, the instrument was seen like a real instrument where one could play an

Figure 3.9: A block based representation of a “patch”

infinite number of notes at the same time, consisting of UGs, whereas the UG wasn’t looked at as an instrument. The implementation of a UG can be on very differing levels, e.g we can construct a UG that can output a series of harmonic sines or we can construct an instrument out of different UG that can do the same.

The UG approach would be faster, nevertheless the concept is the same and there should not be a difference between instruments and UG’s, and even the implementation of UG function should nicely fit in the concept.

Today several systems have dropped the strict distinction between UG’s and instruments. In MAX, for example, the UG are seen as basic object, but the user can build and configure her own UG’s by using the pre-built primitives as a basis. The hierarchical concept can be seen as one of the basic principles of computer music systems [19].

When introducing a hierarchical structure, the question that arises next is always at which level should the hierarchy be built. In general this is answered by the basic rule of “divide and conquer”, meaning to sort out

functionality as good as possible.

Figure 3.9 shows a diagram in the AudioBlocks language, which implements the FM algorithm already mentioned earlier. The interesting feature about this representation is its inherent recursiveness. In Audioblocks every block can be easily split and converted into an abstract block, or higher level UG, like the modulator in this example.

3.6.2 Signal - Control Duality

Another separation in concept manifests itself through the control/event data versus signal data conflict. As already mentioned this distinction was initially made because of performance reasons, but it is still be valid on a higher level of organization because of the more fundamental concepts of how we understand music and signal processing algorithms that produce sound.

The separation of signal and control has lead to two different paradigms in computer music, one dataflow based and the other event based. This gap is also reflected in the language structures that fit with each of the concepts.

[19]

3.6.3 Higher Level Data Handling

Modern signal processing algorithms are more than operations on signals, most of the time they also need higher level structures in order to store transformed data that is not a signal.

The problem of FFT data is solvable within the general context of one dimensional arrays, although not without introducing some additional quirks. Most computer music systems until now handled spectral data mainly internally, inside the UG. This means that spectral data does not have to be

handled by the UG data types used for communication between them, because the UG just take audio input, calculate their spectral algorithm and send out audio data again.

The traditional control rate - signal rate approach leaves the systems already with two different data types, now, if we want to have spectral data as yet another data type the “patching” analogy start to fall apart, graphical representations with different data types are hard to read and understand, because a deep knowledge of datatypes and the operations permitted on them is needed. Furthermore processing of FFT or higher level spectral data needs a special set of UG’s.

As a possible solution we might look at the FFT implementation of Pure Data, where the block computation principle is reused to define FFT frames. A Pd signal processing patch has two additional properties that can be changed. These are the blocksize (defaults to 64) and the overlap (defaults to 1). When doing FFT calculations the parameters can be set to values better fit to FFT frames, blocksize 4096 and overlap 4 for example. This way all the standard UG’s can be used in the spectral domain too.

3.7 Language Concepts

We have seen that some traditional computer music languages developed into domain specific languages (DSL) at some point (examples are CSound, MAX and SAOL). Although a DSL is easier to learn and to apply in its domain, it bears the danger of getting too restrictive when new algorithms and techniques appear. As backwards compatibility is a main concern, the language tend to develop special solutions in order to get over their problems. Other systems use general purpose programming languages, which, in turn

can also be classified regarding different criteria.

3.7.1 Domain Specific Languages

The Music N language, seen as a programming language has the interesting property of being a declarative [62], rather than an imperative, language. The score file is merely static data, which triggers the Music-N instruments, but it follows clearly an imperative paradigm.

This duality in terms of programming language properties doesn't come as a surprise, and it is commonly reflected in the separation of control and signal processing into two languages or as separate concepts. For a language to be useable as a general computer music language it has to be possible to express both concepts.

3.7.2 Functional Programming

Functional programming languages are said to be a subgroup of declarative languages. Languages like LISP have a long tradition in computer music, and the functional approach lends itself very nicely to the UG concept.

One of the principal concepts of functional programming is the lack of side effects. The pure functional approach does not have assignments, and in this sense each computation is only local. E.g. the state of closures is not accessible from the outside of the closure.

3.7.3 Object Oriented Programming

The object oriented approach to programming is probably the mostly used programming paradigm in general, a popularity that was also reflected in the proliferation of computer music systems in object oriented languages.

The description of UG as objects is straightforward and very helpful. An object can incorporate the duality of event based and signal flow based computation, by acting as a Closure or Functor in the signal processing domain, and as an object with its configuration parameters for the event processing.

3.8 Conclusions

In this chapter I have given an overview of general concepts. I mainly described the concepts that reappear in several implementations of computer music languages. For some of the problems there is a more or less clear solution, others are still subject to research, like the scheduling and data passing, the graphical representation, as well as the polyphony. In general the difficulty in designing a CMS lies in the compromise that has to be taken between simplicity, readability, flexibility and speed.

Chapter 4

Design and Implementation of a Prototype

In this chapter I will attempt to define a computer music system based on the concepts outlined in the previous chapters. I will present two research systems that I have implemented and been working with, the first a library for signal processing, the other one a more general framework which allows to experiment with different concepts of programming in computer music. I will also describe a graphical language for patch building, which tries to overcome some of the problems of known systems for graphical programming.

4.1 Goals of a Computer Music System

First a summary of the objectives for a computer music system.

4.1.1 Target User

The primary target user of our system is the musician. Computer musicians want to discover new sounds, new music and new ways to express themselves

using digital tools. This doesn't mean that the system has to be usable by musicians directly without training, but it means that it has to be learn-able and manageable by a person without deep engineering background.

4.1.2 Intuitiveness

During the past years the computer music community has been able to build up a set of techniques and a vocabulary to describe them. A naive user of a computer music system would have a hard time using it without knowing the basic concepts like digital representation of sound, unit generators and basic sound synthesis algorithms. A system is intuitive if it maps well to the generally accepted techniques.

4.1.3 Incremental Development

The system should allow for incremental development. Using CM systems is for the most part some sort of programming. I had experience with a system that allowed for a tight programming-testing loop, which helps the unexperienced user a lot to achieve her goal. Key properties are flexible visual and audio feedback and the possibility to interact with the growing program from the very beginning. This is different from the top-down design approach of standard computer programs, and I consider it as the most important part of a system for creative production.

4.1.4 Extensibility

The difficulty in writing a complete CMS is probably that it is impossible to know what synthesis algorithms or techniques will emerge in the future. That's why a CMS should offer the possibility to be extended within its

domain.

Also it is desirable that the system can be extended into other domains, for computer music it is specifically interesting to be combined with computer graphics.

It is interesting that in fact several of the event based paradigms from computer music apply equally well to interactive computer graphics, as shown by the Pure Data add-on library Gem [14] (Graphics Environment for Multimedia).

4.1.5 Interaction

A modern CMS should allow for real-time interaction, but without penalizing the non-realtime batch processing possibilities. Another important aspect of interaction is the possibility to design user interfaces for the system. This does not have to be within the system itself, but probably by using a protocol like Open Sound Control (OSC) [72].

4.1.6 Portability

We have seen that several CMS died out because of portability problems. This should be avoided at all cost. As we are targeting specifically for embedded platforms, we can not even depend on a specific floating point data type. It should also be avoided to depend on too many additional libraries.

4.1.7 Efficiency

The system should be efficient. Usability of a realtime CMS goes hand in hand with efficiency. Also a more efficient system can lead to more complex and interesting instruments.

4.1.8 Research

It should allow for fast prototyping for researchers who want to implement and experiment with new algorithms. Writing of an application around an algorithm for presentation or dissemination is tedious work. Traditionally computer CMS have been extensively used for implementing new algorithms.

4.1.9 Musical Openness

Some of the CMS define musical structures. This is a good thing and helps the musician, we think though that all musical structure should be expressible within the system, not limiting it to a certain way of thinking about music. Hence musical structure should be built using the system, but not as a built-in concept.

4.2 Drawbacks of Existing Systems

After almost 50 years of computer music systems we have a huge collection of different implementations. The system evolved into what we are using now. Nevertheless our current systems still have limitations. A good design strategy for a new computer music system could therefore be to try to identify and avoid mistakes that were made before and not introduce new ones.

4.2.1 Text Based Languages and Interaction

With a text based language it has been traditionally pretty hard to interact. Interactivity and the possibility of changing code should have a high priority.

4.2.2 The Graphical Programming Paradigm

Although graphical programming is a good way to abstract the construction of UG graphs it is not as straight forward when used as a programming language. It seems that algorithms that are simple to express in a procedural language might be awkward to write in a graphical one.

Also a lot time is spend by drawing lines between objects and trying to arrange the objects in order to be readable and understandable at all.

4.2.3 Complexity

In order to support new synthesis algorithms several systems have reached a substantial complexity, which is partly due to the need of being backwards compatible and to adapt the system to new concepts. A proliferation of extensions with overlapping functionality for some systems is not good for the usability of a system.

4.3 Putting it together

4.3.1 The Interface

In order for a computer music language to be easy to learn and intuitive at the patching level, it is important to offer a graphical user interface. At the same time, several tasks like instantiating the same object iteratively and with different parameters are a lot easier to express in a scripting language. Our proposal for a computer music system is therefore a language that combines both, scripting and patching in a closely integrated way.

As an example, if a UG is put into the system graphically, the corresponding command gets introduced into the listener of the interpreter, and

the object is put on the canvas. The same thing happens the other way around.

Patching of objects should be naturally expressible in the scripting language, (see also the different possibilities of textual patch construction discussed in the previous chapter).

Scripting and patching should be two representations of the same internal commands.

Graphical patching is semantically not as expressive as scripting, therefore the graphical representation will be a subset of the languages syntax only. Some low level behaviors will only be expressible in the scripting language, but by encapsulating them in function they are turned into “patchable” objects.

4.3.2 The Language

The syntax of the scripting language plays an important role when learning a language, especially if the user has previous experience with programming. It is therefore desirable to avoid new concepts, syntactically it should be avoided to introduce new operators that carry meaning different from the “standard” mathematical one. As structural elements some of the punctuation signs are unavoidable, like “(,)” for function call and “.” in order to access higher level data structures. The symbols “[“ and “]” seem to be the standard marks for array access, another important feature of a language for music and DSP.

On the category level, the language should support object oriented as well as functional concepts. A general set of control structures and realtime garbage collection.

The research community has produced hundreds of different languages, instead of implementing our own one the best choice would be to extend an

existing one. It should also be taken into account to design the system in a way that more than one scripting language can be supported.

4.3.3 Concurrency

In a language for computer music concurrency is a fundamental requirement. More than being able to schedule several tasks at the same time it is also important to have the possibility of synchronization between these tasks. Explicit scheduling on the user level is the common strategy that is used to achieve this goal.

4.3.4 Design of Basic Building Blocks

Although the exact definition of which UG's should be built-in into the computer music system has been handled on an abstract layer until now only, it is nevertheless important to design a set that enables flexibility at the same time as offering basic structures that complement each other and form an orthogonal set of what is considered to be necessary in order to implement most of the current sound synthesis algorithms.

4.4 Three studies: Toluene, ALUA and AudioBlocks

In this section I describe three research systems that I have built in order to explore ideas about the structure and possible implementation of computer music systems. Appendix A describes yet another system, that was specifically built in order to estimate the speed loss that is involved when using interpreted languages, and appendix B describes an the successful effort of

porting the Pure Data computer music system to handheld devices, a Pure Data version called PDa which is in wide use already and has proved its stability in during long term sound installations.

The systems I have built come conceptually and timely one after the other. The first system, Toluene, is an attempt to construct a MATLAB like API on top of C++, the other system ALUA, expands the general scripting language Lua [35] with realtime audio functionality. In order to evaluate the feasibility of a computer music system on embedded devices the Lua language, which has only one type to represent numbers, which traditionally is the `c` type “float” has been adapted to work with fixed point numbers.

AudioBlocks exists as a concept and is meant as a graphical extension of ALUA.

4.4.1 Toluene

Toluene is an extension to the Template Numerical Toolkit (TNT) array definition for C++. Figure 4.1 shows an example of reading a soundfile, doing an FFT of its left channel applying a frequency domain lowpass filter with linear slope, do an IFFT and send it to the sound output.

The extensions to the TNT toolkit consist of:

- Soundfile reading and writing into TNT arrays
- Sound input and output from TNT arrays
- constant value array operations
- FFT, IFFT operations
- TNT array operations for mathematical functions like `sin()`, `cos()` etc.

```
int main(int argc, char** argv)
{
    // Open the sound output and a soundfile to read
    SoundDevice out;
    out.open("test");
    SoundFile file(argv[1]);

    // Setup the Wave
    Wave c(2048);
    Wave d(2048);
    Wave shape(2048);
    Wave imag = shape.subarray(1025,2048);

    // Calculate the spectral filter
    ramp(shape,1.,-1./1024.);
    ramp(imag,1.,-1./1024.);

    while (file.read(c,d)) {
        rfft(c);
        c *= shape;
        irfft(c);

        c*=1./2048.;
        out.write(c);
    }
    return 0;
}
```

Figure 4.1: FFT - IFFT calculation using Toluene

- fast TNT array permutations (e.g. circular shift without temporal storage)
- Graphical interface for displaying arrays with zoom, scale, etc.
- statistical operations of arrays (max, min, sum, mean, etc ...)

TNT defines a *Wave* class, which derives from *Array1D < float >*, and enhances the *Array1D* type, mainly by supplying in place calculations of the TNT and Toluene array calculations.

As can be seen from the example, the code is very compact, the most extensive part is the setup of the filter array, sound output device and the *Waves* that are used to do the calculation, the while loop does the real work by applying a FFT to the wave, multiplying the spectral magnitude with the spectral filter and converting the resulting values back into the time domain.

An advantage of using a standardized array type like TNT is its support for the routines outlined in the “Numerical Recipes for C++” [71] through the `nutil_tnt.h` header.

4.4.2 ALUA

ALUA is a language for prototyping computer music systems. Its backend is the fast and flexible Lua [35] extension language. ALUA has a kernel part that is written in C and offers basic audio I/O functionality. The rest of the ALUA system is written in LUA code itself. Writing in LUA allows for very fast prototyping and changes in the structure without having to care about the low level parts of a computer music system. Once established the final API for the system, the UG’s written in LUA can be replaced by their Toluene counterparts, or by any other compiled and optimized UG implementation.

```
audio.start()

-- Setup the computation chain

fmindex = Const(1000)
envelope = Env(200,700,1000)
fmnote = Mult(envelope,Sine(Add(250,Mult(fmindex,Sine(125)))))

o = Out(Mult(0.6,fmnote))

-- Play the patch, a line of 16 FM tones

for i=1,16 do
play(o,200)
envelope(10,80,80+(16-i)*20)
index(i*500)
end
```

Figure 4.2: ALUA program for playing an FM line

The ALUA program in figure 4.4.2 has two parts, similar to a Music-N score. The first part is the setup of the instrument (or patch). LUA supports very well functional principles, therefore our UG implementation are functions. The examples shows a UG graph similar to the one already seen in Figure 3.8, a simple FM generator.

With ALUA the orchestra can be generated algorithmically, as described in Section 3.2.3.

This time the setup part is a bit different, as it stores some of the UG's in variables. Assigning variable names to UG's allows us later to change their parameters. The data returned by the unit generators during setup are functions, which can be used to change the internal states of the UGs when the program is running.

The parameter changing is made possible because of LUA's way of passing

variables to functions. This way, we can change values stored in closures, and hence we have access to all the parameters of the UG's.

The second part "Play the patch" shows how we play 16 notes, each one with a slightly different envelope (the envelope variable) and a different frequency modulation index (the findex UG).

The `play(o,200)` call advances the time for 200 ms and calculates the signal in realtime.

As can be seen, ALUA is a language that gets explicitly scheduled, the user can decide at which granularity to change the parameters by changing the second parameter of the `play()` function.

Another subtle notion of the above code is that ALUA uses complex UG's as parameters instead of simple values. In order to have a constant parameter, numerical value get converted into a Const UG, which in turn can be changed the same way as any other UG.

Although ALUA is a research system only it is already fully useable as a command line driven computer music system.

4.4.3 AudioBlocks

Although graphical programming didn't succeed in the general purpose programming world, the concept that computer music builds on leads directly to graphical programming. [39],[54]. Recent systems have adopted these approaches, but seldom tried to change the graphical concepts, except in the look and feel of the application. This is a proposal for an improved - and different - patching language, that tries to remedy some of the drawbacks in standard graphical patching languages. First I would like to outline some of the principles taken from Pure Data, that I think are important for a graphical language, but which might not be obvious.[55]

Figure 4.3: FM synthesis AudioBlocks patch

- text boxes, not icons as representations of functionality
- the text should define the function of the box entirely
- no hidden variables, states

Figure 4.4.3 shows a patch in a new designed graphical language “AudioBlocks”. The first major difference, AudioBlocks is not in need of patch chords. The connection of two objects is defined by their adjacency. Boxes can have several input slots (called inlets), but only one output slot (outlet). Which inlet gets connected is determined by the position of the source audioblock (audioblock is the AudioBlock expression for signal processing object).

The AudioBlock language has a built-in notion of organization and structure. AudioBlock subpatches build themselves semi-automatically and evolve directly from the programming. AudioBlock forces the user to a structured programming style.

AudioBlocks have one output, but can have several inputs. The inputs are filled up from left to right by the blocks above a certain UG, like the “Add” in Figure 4.4.3). This disallows the omission of inputs, which in turn reflects the workings of the scripting language.

The primary goal is to have the same conceptual structure in the graphical language as we have in the scripting language. The assignment of a branch of the graph to a variable in ALUA, corresponds to the “findex” block in AudioBlocks, and in fact has the same purpose, the possibility to reuse a branch and plug it into another UG.

Also, by updating the “findex” block, the parameters of the “MULT” function (the last one of the block) can be changed, which in turn leads to a change in the modulator index.

Chapter 5

Future Work

Creating music with a computer is about interaction. Music, as a time based medium, is hard to capture with the static concepts we use when working with a computer. Therefore the needs of computer music languages are different than the needs for other programming languages. The creative process when making music is different from the one of designing and implementing general computer software.

5.1 Implementation Details

Although not my main focus, there is still a lot of work to be done until ALUA is a fully usable language for computer music. The basic UG set is not yet completed, as well as the optimized UG implementations are still missing.

5.2 Just-in-time Programming

A main concern for computer music systems is to abstract the low level sound processing algorithms into a language that is easily understandable and flexible enough to express musical ideas and implement them. The challenge in building a computer music system is to construct a system that is easy to use and powerful at the same time.

One key aspect of this problem is the development process of a computer music piece (or program). Experimentation is one of the main strategies in finding solutions. As I have outlined in the previous chapter, I consider the tight programming, testing, debugging cycle that computer systems like Max/Pd, SuperCollider, ChuckK or some interpreter based system allow a crucial point.

In these systems the user can interact with the DSP graph and the general computing structure directly, while the program is running. These technique is also called “live coding”, “just in time programming”, “on-the-fly programming” or “dynamic patching”, in the performance context, but comes directly from the need of experimentation with the computer music program in a creative context.

Main issues to address in this area are:

- The technique of using a fast coding - testing turnaround can lead to working, but badly structured programs. Especially the MAX paradigm has shown that the development of bigger projects fails without a clear design in advance. The language should enforce structured programming.
- With a new approach to graphical programming and structuring of the code structured programming should be enforced. Although a concept

of how such a system could look like has been outline in the previous chapter, its general usefulness still needs to be verified.

- One crucial aspect of this iterative approach to programming is the visual and sonic feedback of the running system. This will form a main focus for my future work
- One important aspect of a computer music system is teaching the principles of computer music. It has to be verified in an educational context if the system is really easier to handle and powerful enough.

5.3 Programming Languages

Another aspect of programming is the programming language that is used. Clearly, it is desirable to use a high level programming language, with a clear syntax, that deals with all the task the user should not directly be in contact, like memory management, variable declarations and pointers.

It is also desirable to have a limited set of types, as types generate ambiguity in commands and the language in general.

The language I have chosen for the prototype fulfills most of these requirements. Lua has only one major high level type, the table, which acts at the same time as array, “C”-like structure, class and hash table. Lua has very few special characters, can be used interactively, is efficient and has a realtime garbage collector.

Other programming languages have to be evaluated for their adaptability as a scripting language for the system.

Lua is a language that can be shaped perfectly towards ones needs, but the more it is customized the slower it will run.

This means that once found the final syntax of our system it might have to be implemented as a customized language.

5.4 Conclusions

The most interesting aspect of new computer music systems seems to be the interaction of the musician with the system. The possibility to facilitate the access of the user to new techniques. One interesting pattern of interaction that we found to work very well in this context is what might be called “incremental programming”, the possibility to make small changes try out the effect and be able to go back, exploring the system, rather than programming.

Appendix A

An Interpreted Language for Real Time Signal Processing

This article was presented in the 2002 International Computer Musik Conference. It was put in the appendix as a reference, the interpreted language it describes reached its goal in some cases (it was fast), but it never developed into a useable system.

A.1 Abstract

Real time signal processing for music generation has been affordable for several years now, due to the tremendous increase in the performance of computer systems. Parallel to that development several signal processing engines have been built, which are specifically targeted to real time processing, and hence make it easier for the electronic musician to build costume applications [51] [24]. Additionally they offer fast prototyping systems for researchers. Unfortunately these system are limited in that they only offer block wise arithmetic.

This paper investigates possibilities and performance of interpreted languages for signal processing tasks, in order to overcome these limitations. As an example, the performance of an implementation of a Forth like language is given.

A.2 Introduction

Due to performance issues, most existing real time signal processing systems use block arithmetic. They are not specifically fit for research work, as block arithmetic, which in some cases is sufficient for algorithms in the audio domain, definitely is not sufficient when developing algorithms in the spectral domain.

The common way to surpass this limitation until now has been to write dedicated code in a low level language such as C, in order to have access to single data samples. This approach is not always well suited for several reasons.

C is a rather lowlevel and insecure language, programming in C therefore needs a certain amount of experience. Basically the same applies to C++.

Researchers who are able to program in a compiled language, loose too much time in the coding, compilation, testing cycle, i.e. they prefer an interleaved coding/testing approach and therefore develop their algorithms on platforms like Matlab that offer an easier way to change and adjust their algorithms.

Naturally it is desirable that the resulting system is a runnable prototype or even better a finished application. With existing systems this is either not possible, or only by introducing further optimization steps, which could or could not lead to a system that runs in realtime.

The goal is therefore to develop an interpreter with a performance that lies in the same range as a costume “C” implementation for a given algorithm. At the first thought this might look very hard, but we have the advantage of having a very well defined field of application for our interpreter, and can therefore target its structure to our needs.

The basic structure of stack engines makes it possible to write very fast interpreters. This structure is discussed in the first part of the paper.

The system discussed in the second part adds functionality specifically for signal processing and takes into account the goals that should be reached by the interpreter.

Some examples show the system applied to different algorithms in signal processing and their performance in comparison to implementation in C and other programming languages.

A.3 Implementation Considerations

Interpreted languages generally depend on some virtual machine representation on which the basic commands are executed. In order to make this virtual machine hardware independent, it is commonly based on stack engines. A stack engine, as opposed to register engines, keeps values in a data stack instead of registers. Each command is working with the values that are on top of the stack.

The postfix notation is a natural consequence of this stack based design. The natural order of the commands to perform an addition is:

1. push **value1** onto the stack
2. push **value2** onto the stack

3. **add** the two values on top of the stack and replace them with the result of the computation.

resulting in a command like “**4 5 add**”.

The basic operations map directly to forth code, therefore making forth some sort of “assembler” for stack-based engines.

Another example of such a stack engine is the Java virtual machine. Commonly virtual machines offer different services, depending on the concrete needs of the corresponding interpreter.

Knowing the implementation of interpreters we can ask ourselves what makes interpreters slower than compilers.

There are two main reasons why interpreters are slower. First, there is a slowdown caused by the mapping of the virtual machine to the real hardware. A software implementation of a stack on a register based machine always adds additional operations and memory accesses for each instruction. Secondly, the operation scheduling is done in software, adding a constant overhead to every instruction for scheduling to the next instruction.

Both of the problems have been studied and solutions have been proposed, leading in one case to the development of hardware stacks for dedicated forth hardware and hardware implementations of Java engines and on the other hand to different techniques to improve the performance like threading, stack caching and just in time compilation.

A.3.1 Threading [30, 40]

Different techniques of threading are known, each of them has its own advantages and disadvantages. Subroutine threading adds a subroutine for each interpreter command (This technique is commonly used in existing computer music systems such as CSound and the different MAX slangs). Other

threading techniques include in direct threading and direct threading. On modern processors direct threading seems to be the fastest solution. In direct threaded systems, there is a direct jump from one implementation of a command to the next, avoiding calls to subroutines and the more expensive switch statement.

A.3.2 Stack Caching

Threading addresses the first overhead within interpreters, namely the instruction scheduling. To improve the performance of the software stack machine implementation commonly a technique called “stack caching” is performed. Stack caching holds some elements from the stack within registers of the register based hardware. This method has the drawback, that frequently used operations like push and pop get more expensive. Commonly this method is used with only the “Top of Stack” held in a register. Holding more than one element of the stack in registers adds a certain amount of logistic overhead to the implementation, which therefore not always results in better performance [41].

A.3.3 Common Interpreters

Commonly used fast interpreters like Ocaml (an ML based object oriented functional language) and Smalltalk use similar approaches to optimize speed. The same concepts can be found in the Java virtual machine interpreter.

The system used for the benchmarks is a Forth like interpreter. It is implemented from scratch, in order to avoid side effects from an integration into an unknown system and to have full control over the optimizations applied. A look on the implementation of the kaffe virtual Java engine revealed no such optimizations in interpreted mode.

Commonly it can be said that existing optimizations do not specifically target one concrete use of the the engine, but they try to improve general performance.

A.4 An Interpreter for Signal Processing

The first thing that is done when making a scripting language fit for real time DSP, numerical python, matlab,.. is adding vector computation commands. This hasn't been done yet for the benchmarks, as the bench marking target is on a lower, sample based, computation level. Benchmarking different vector computation algorithms isn't in the scope of this paper, the goal of the system is not having a extensive slowdown in doing sample wise computation, so that the possibility of vector computations within the language itself is given.

The initial goal of developing the interpreter was to use it as an extension to already existing Computer Music Systems, specifically an implementation for the "PD" language was made. This goal in mind the engine is lacking several features normally found in programming languages. It uses a very simplified memory model, there is no such thing as garbage collection, object orientation, or even the possibility of function definitions. Whereas this is quite sufficient for implementing small algorithms, another approach has to be taken when the target is a self contained system. One solution would be to apply the discussed techniques to an already existing interpreted language.

Several other techniques can be applied in order to make the language even faster.

A.4.1 The Floating Point Stack

Applying the known techniques of direct threading and stack caching improved the performance of the system as can be seen in the results section. The implemented engine has a separate integer and floating point stack, implementing a stack caching system for the floating point stack led to a performance loss on the Pentium III processor. Obviously the compiler used (gcc) didn't translate the C-code into the desired assembly instructions, leading to additional overhead when trying to do stack caching with floating point registers.

The solution to this problem, on Intel architectures, lies close at hand. The arithmetic coprocessor is implemented as a stack engine, therefore the mapping from virtual instruction to machine instructions is one-to-one in most cases, making the overhead of the interpreter for floating point calculation only dependent from the scheduling overhead.

A.4.2 Parsing

The simple structure of the system makes it possible to include some sort of compilation into the text parsing state of the system. Generally the text parsing is already some sort of compilation, which in the first stages only consisted of a direct "token to bytecode" mapping. Most of the algorithms in signal processing consists of looping over arrays of data. Knowing that the body of the loop could be taken, arranged without the scheduling instructions (in direct threading these proved to be 3 instructions at the end of each word), and then used as one single bytecode should further speed up the calculations. Parsing is done in the startup of the system and has proved to be very fast. It has to be considered that this phase is equivalent to both, the compilation

phase for java programs, and the JIT compilation performed at runtime.

A.4.3 Type and Memory Checks

The interpreter described lacks one basic feature which is commonly connected with interpreters. It is inherently insecure, making it possible to access objects on the stack with wrong operations (it is not type safe) and even worse it is possible to access memory regions that lead to segmentation faults. In order to avoid any overhead produced by these checks during runtime, a two way approach has to be taken.

First, the parser should be implemented in a way to be able to do type checking, but additional type checking at runtime is unavoidable.

In this case all speed assumptions made here would be invalid, because they don't take the type checks into account [20].

There is a way around this, by implementing two different parsers, which would make it possible to parse the code into type and memory safe or into performance versions, similar to the debug and release versions of C programs.

This doesn't guarantee absolute security, but most of the problems are visible during development with the secure version, and there will still be no speed degradation in the runtime version.

A.5 Results

Several tests have been performed, in order to compare the speed of the interpreter to a compiled C version of the same algorithm. The Algorithms used are:

Figure A.1: Performance of the FIR filter

Figure A.2: Performance of Scaling for different optimization settings

- **Scaling** Here the loop consists of one floating point operation and the corresponding memory fetch and store operations.
- **Basic Fir Filter** Several fetch/store, multiplications and additions in the loop body.
- **Peak Detection** This includes some flow control changes.

All of the tests were made with different settings. The output is the ratio between the compiled and the interpreted version of the algorithm. It has to be stated, that the implementations in C are not specifically tuned, so

Figure A.3: Performance of the Peak picking algorithm for different optimization settings

they give an expectation of what a programmer would do without tuning the implementation by hand, like loop enrolling, specific register usage, etc. On the other hand, the interpreted code has been carefully tuned, because this tuning is giving us an insight of what we need for the specific task, and can therefore be regarded as one of the main tools that let to our results.

A.6 Conclusion

The performance comparison showed good results for the interpreter prototype. It is shown that in order to achieve good performance every possible optimization strategy has to be applied.

The next step is to reduce scheduling overhead by compiling the parts of the loop into machine native format during text parsing. This step is not very complicated and should yield to a significant speedup. This gives hope that the system will stay in a small and manageable state, so it can easily be incorporated as already existing system as scripting extension language for DSP.

One drawback of the system is its reverse notation and other syntactically inherent problems, which make it hard to learn the language. Future work includes deciding on a final syntax. The goal is to keep the development system small by not introducing a complicated bytecode compiler, and therefore stay rather close to standard forth notation.

Further improvement in syntax and speed should be possible through higher level builtin vector functions and dedicated signal processing bytecodes.

A long term goal would be to make the system independent from any other higher level computer music language.

Appendix B

PDa: Real Time Signal Processing and Sound Generation on Handheld Devices

This article for the Computer Music Conference 2003 describes work done with the computer music system Pure Data. It shows some of the strength of the Free Software concept, in that Pure Data is probably the first computer music system running on a handheld device, and in this sense already pointing towards a possible future of computing.

B.1 Abstract

Not too long ago real time audio synthesis and signal processing used to be restricted to dedicated hardware. In the mid-nineties software synthesizers entered the field of desktop computing.

At the same time software for real-time computer music systems moved from dedicated DSP's to desktop computers with diverging operating systems. PD (Pure Data) is a computer music systems that showed a great deal of flexibility, originally designed to run on SGI Irix and Windows NT machines, it has been ported to Linux in 1997 and runs on all major Desktop operating systems nowadays.

This was only possible because of its openness and availability as free software. This paper describes a new port of PD, this time not for a new operating system but for a new type of computers: the PocketPC. The paper describes the capabilities of these small handheld devices nowadays and then goes on to describe different aspects of the software system derived from PD and called PDa.

B.2 Introduction

Computing devices get smaller and faster every year. With more or less powerful computers that can be carried around in the pocket being a reality, the question is what does this mean for computer music. One obvious advantage is that computer musicians will be more mobile, it will be possible for them to carry around their instrument. But the concept offers more possibilities than just being able to experiment with computer music wherever you are.

New ideas of controlling computer music instruments have to be developed in order to take full advantage of the newly gained mobility.

Combining these handheld devices with wireless networking will offer new ways of collaboration and interaction between computer musicians.

All of this is not reality yet, different obstacles have to be overcome, but the most important steps are taken, and running a classical computer music

tool like PD on a handheld device surely proves the feasibility.

The problems to overcome can be split into three main topics. First, how to solve the constraints of handheld devices in terms of performance.

Second, how will it be possible to work and develop on these devices, most of the time there is no keyboard, and the user interface basically consists of a touch-screen and a few buttons.

Third, how is it possible after having built a patch, to control the resulting instrument.

B.3 Handheld Devices

The most powerful processors that are available today for handhelds are Intel StrongARM and XScale processors, with a clock frequency of 200 and up to 400 MHz. Considering that the fastest desktop had 400 MHz not too many years ago and powerful sound applications were possible back then already, the performance problem seems to be easy to solve at a first glance.

This is of course not the case, because small devices have several restrictions that full grown computer systems do not have. On the other hand in some domains they are not that far behind.

B.3.1 Sound Quality

One might think that handheld devices would have a far inferior sound quality, they have integrated sound chips, and common experience from laptop computers tells us that integrated sound tends to be of low quality.

Taking a closer look reveals some surprise, though. The specification does not look that bad, the sound chip on the iPaq supports 2 channels 44.1kHz, CD quality sound. The chip used in the iPaq is Philips UDA1341TS, a chip

designed for MiniDisc portable players, the data sheet of the chip [48] reveals a over-sampling ratio of 128, a S/N ratio of 100dB (sic).

Because of the design of the handheld this sound quality is conserved in the device, there is no interference of harddisks, no moving parts or influences from the power supply. The sound quality is excellent.

The system where tests have been carried out is a Compaq iPaq. The only audio input on these devices is a builtin microphone, therefore the audio input is of very low quality.

B.3.2 Processing Power

The core of the most powerful handheld devices nowadays is based on the the Advanced RISC Machines (ARM) 32 bit embedded microprocessors [33]. This technology has become the most popular chip in use today. Its newest implementation is the PXA255 XScale processor, a pure RISC processor with binary compatibility with the older StrongARM processors, that supports clock speeds up to 400 MHz and several other speed enhancements, like code-compression in order to reduce instruction code size and a Multiply Accumulate (MAC) instruction, borrowed from DSP (Digital Signal Processing) technology.

Besides that the StrongARM processor has every feature that a modern RISC engine needs, hit-under-miss cache managment, instruction pipeline and branch prediction. The only thing that makes it different from common Desktop microprocessors is its lack of a floating point unit.

As signal processing software written in higher level languages like C has been concentrated around using IEEE-754 32 bit floating point numbers, and the floating point emulation of the ARM processors is slow, this fact is a major obstacle for porting applications to ARM architectures.

B.3.3 Memory and Peripherals

It can be said that handheld devices offer a reasonable amount of memory which is about 64 MB [28]. HP's (formerly Compaqs) iPaqs are extensible devices. Using an adaptor for Compaq Flash cards, the system can be extended with different peripherals, ranging from additional memory cards (the base system comes with 48MB of flash memory) to wireless network cards and CF format hard disks. PCMCIA extensions are supported too, making it theoretically possible to use PCMCIA multichannel soundcards.

B.4 Computer Music on PocketPC

B.4.1 PD and Linux

PD [51] is a free software implementation of a computer music system based on the MAX paradigm. One of its outstanding features might be its compactness of code. This has led to the decision to use PD as a base for doing software development on handheld devices, rather than writing new software from scratch.

The current implementation runs on Linux only[66], although there is nothing Linux specific in the code. This means that it probably can easily be reused on the Windows PocketPC platform. The choice for Linux was based on the fact that all necessary tools were easily available.

B.4.2 The Performance

Preliminary tests showed quick results, because of the fact that getting PD to start on the iPaq was merely the task of recompiling it. The performance was bad though, so the system could not be used to do real-time audio processing.

Audio off	7 %
10 oscillators	35 %
20 oscillators	51 %
30 oscillators	68 %
40 oscillators	87 %

Table B.1: Performance on a 200MHz StrongARM processor

In order to improve the performance, all floating point calculation had to be avoided, specially for the data-flow part which is very performance intensive.

Avoiding floating point calculations means basically to replace every signal processing object that exists with an integer version [56] [11]. Luckily PD has a small and orthogonal set of base objects.

Table 1 shows some performance measurements (the typical number of sine oscillators benchmark) of the ported objects. The patches consist of oscillators, audio output and signal adders. The integer only version should have a speedup on standard computers too.

B.4.3 Programming with PDA

As mentioned above, the limited possibilities of user input on handheld devices makes it hard to write patches on the iPaq. This is definitely a field where a lot of improvement is possible. Up to now the patching happened on a desktop machine, running the equivalent version of PD, then the patches are transferred to the handheld and played there. It is possible to edit patches on the handheld devices itself, but at the time being it is much more cumbersome.

B.4.4 Controlling the System

The direct way to control the patches on the iPaq is through the touch screen and buttons of the device. The touch-screen delivers data with two degrees of freedom. Handheld devices commonly have character recognition software installed, the software that comes with the iPaq Linux distribution offers a program called `xstroke` for this purpose. `Xstroke` allows to define new character mappings in a configuration file, making it the ideal tool for recognizing gestures on the touch-screen in order to improve the control.

All of these control input parameters can be mapped via their PD objects to events in the patch.

Of course it would be advantageous to have external controllers. This is possible through the serial port that is builtin in the iPaq. Accessing the serial port is straight forward by using PD's externals for serial port. There is a wide range of controllers that can be used this way. [34]

B.5 Future Directions

Future work will mainly focus on improving the integration of the software in the handheld device and on finding new ways to control the system. Linking together several handheld devices via wireless networks and exchanging synchronization and control data is another field that will be very interesting.

Having a new technology available to generate music is always a challenging experience, only the future will show what kind of applications this will have.

In order to make the system easier accessible it could be recompiled on other PocketPC operating system such as WindowsCE or PocketPC 2002.

B.6 Conclusions

PDA delivers a proof of concept, it shows one direction into which computer music systems might go in the future, probably similar to the laptop computer music revolution we saw in the last few years. The performance figures show that we are not too early with this work, which hopefully will be one way to cross boundaries and open new paths to computer music practice.

Bibliography

- [1] A. Freed A. Chaudhary and M. Wright. An open architecture for real-time music software. In *Proceedings of International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 2000. International Computer Music Association.
- [2] Curtis Abbott. The 4CED program. *Computer Music Journal*, 5(1), 1981.
- [3] Xavier Amatriain. *An Object-Oriented Metamodel for Digital Signal Processing*. PhD thesis, Pompeu Fabra University, 2004.
- [4] David P. Anderson and Ron Kuivila. Formula: A programming language for expressive computer music. *Computer*, 24:12–21, July 1991.
- [5] X. Arumí, P. Amatriain. Clam, an object-oriented framework for audio and music. In *Proceedings of 3rd International Linux Audio Conference; Karlsruhe, Germany*, 2005.
- [6] Gerard Assayag. Computer assisted composition at ircam: From patchwork to open music. *Computer Music Journal*, 23(3), 1999.
- [7] Emmanuel Bacry. Lastwave. <http://www.cmap.polytechnique.fr/~bacry/LastWave>.

- [8] Ross Bencina. Oasis rose the composition - real-time DSP with AudioMulch. In *Proceedings of the Australian Computer Music Conference*, pages 10–12, Canberra, July 1998. Australian National University.
- [9] Eli Brandt. *Temporal Type Constructors for Computer Music Programming*. PhD thesis, Carnegie Mellon University, 2002.
- [10] Phil Burk. Jsyn: Real-time synthesis API for Java. In *Proceedings of the Int. Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 1998. International Computer Music Computer Association.
- [11] Charles R. Yates. Fixed-Point Arithmetic. <http://personal.bellsouth.net/~yatesc/fp.pdf>, 14 April 1999.
- [12] D. J. Collinge. MOXIE: a language for computer music performance. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 1984. International Computer Music Association.
- [13] P. Cook and G. Scavone. The synthesis toolkit (stk). In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 1999. Computer Music Association.
- [14] Mark Danks. Real-time image and video processing in GEM. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, pages 220–223, San Francisco, 1997. International Computer Music Association.
- [15] R. Dannenberg. The implementation of nyquist, a sound-synthesis language. *Computer Music Journal*, 21(3):71–82, 1997.
- [16] Roger Dannenberg. A realtime scheduler/dispatcher. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, pages 239–242. Computer Music Association, September 1988.

- [17] Roger Dannenberg and Eli Brandt. A flexible realtime software synthesis system. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, pages 270–273, San Francisco, 1996. Computer Music Association.
- [18] Roger B. Dannenberg. Arctic: A functional language for real-time control. In *LFP '84: Proceedings of the 1984 ACM Symposium on LISP and functional programming*, pages 96–103, New York, NY, USA, 1984. ACM Press.
- [19] Roger B. Dannenberg. A language for interactive audio applications. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 2002. International Computer Music Association, International Computer Music Association.
- [20] Dr. Stephan Becher. Introduction to strongForth. <http://home.t-online.de/home/s.becher/forth/intro.htm>, 2000.
- [21] M. Puckette E. Lindeman and E. Viara. The ircam signal processing workstation - an environment for research in real-time musical signal processing and performance. In *Euro Micro Proceedings*, 1990.
- [22] John W. Eaton. Octave. <http://www.octave.org>.
- [23] M. V. Mathews et al. *The Technology of Computer Music*. MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass., 1969.
- [24] Maurizio De Cecco François Déchelle. The Ircam Real-Time Platform And Applications. *Proceedings of the ICMC conference*, 1995.
- [25] Christopher Fry. Flavors band: An environment for processing musical style. *Computer Music Journal*, 8(4):20–34, 1984.

- [26] Albert Gräf. Q: A functional programming language for multimedia applications. <http://lac.zkm.de/2005/proceedings.shtml>.
- [27] Peter Hanappe. *Design and Implementation of an integrated Environment for Music Composition and Synthesis*. PhD thesis, University of Paris 6, 1999.
- [28] Corp. Hewlett Packard. Compaq iPaq Pocket PC H3900 Series. Data Sheet, 2002.
- [29] Paul Hudak. Haskore music tutorial. In *Advanced Functional Programming*, pages 38–67, 1996.
- [30] Fabio Riccardi Ian Piumarta. Optimizing Direct Threaded Code by Selective Inlining. *Proceedings of the ACM SIGPLAN '98 conference on Programming language design and implementation*, May 1998.
- [31] Julius O. Smith III. Viewpoints on the history of digital synthesis. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, pages 1–10, San Francisco, 1991. Computer Music Association.
- [32] Mathworks Inc. Matlab. <http://www.mathworks.com>.
- [33] Intel Corp. The Intel PXA250 Applications Processor. <http://www.intel.com/design/pca/>, 2003.
- [34] Joseph Paradiso. Electronic Music Interfaces. <http://web.media.mit.edu/~joep/SpectrumWeb/SpectrumX.html>, 1998.
- [35] W. Celes L. H. de Figueiredo, R. Ierusalimschy. The design and implementation of a language for extending applications. In *Proceedings*

- of XXI Brazilian Seminar on Software and Hardware*, pages 273–283, 1994.
- [36] A. Leal L. Hiller and R. A. Baker. *Revised MUSICOMP manual. Tech. Rep. 13*. School of Music, Experimental Music Studio, University of Illinois, Urbana, Ill, 1966.
- [37] Victor Lazzarini. The sound object library. *Organised Sound*, 5(1):35–49, 2000.
- [38] Gareth Loy and Curtis Abbott. Programming languages for computer music synthesis, performance, and composition. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 17(2):235–265, 1985.
- [39] Laursen M. and Dithen J. Patchwork, a graphical language inpreform. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*. International Computer Music Computer Association, 1989.
- [40] M. Anton Ertl. A Portable Forth Engine. *EuroFORTH '93 Conference Proceedings*, 1993.
- [41] M. Anton Ertl. Stack Caching for Interpreters. *SIGPLAN '95 Conference on Programming Language Design and Implementation*, pages 315–327, 1995.
- [42] Donald MacInnis. Sound synthesis by computer: Musigol, a program written entirely in extended algol. *Perspectives of New Music*, 7(1):66–79, 1968.
- [43] Günter Geiger Martin Kaltenbrunner and Sergi Jordà. Dynamic patches for live musical performance. In *Proceedings of the 4th Conference on*

- New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME 04)*, Hamamatsu (Japan), 2004.
- [44] M. V. Mathews and F. R. Moore. GROOVE program to compose, store, and edit functions of time. *Commun. ACM*, 13(12):715–721, 1970.
- [45] Max Mathews and J. Pasquale. RTSKED, a scheduled performance language for the crumar general development system. In *Proceedings of the 1981 International Computer Music Conference*, page 286, San Francisco, 1981. International Computer Music Association.
- [46] James McCartney. A new, flexible framework for audio and image synthesis. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, pages 258–261, San Francisco, 2000. International Computer Music Association.
- [47] Richard L. White Perry Greenfield, Todd Miller and J. C. Hsu. numarray. http://www.stsci.edu/resources/software_hardware/numarray.
- [48] Philips Semiconductors. UDA1341TS - Economy audio CODEC for MiniDisc (MD) home stereo and portable applications, 16 May 2002.
- [49] Steven Travis Pope. The Musical Object Development Environment (MODE) – ten years of music software in Smalltalk. In *Proceedings of the 1994 International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 1994. International Computer Music Computer Association.
- [50] Roldan Pozo. Template numerical toolkit. <http://math.nist.gov/tnt>.
- [51] M. Puckette. Pure data: another integrated computer music environment. In *Proc. the Second Intercollege Computer Music Concerts*, pages 37–41, 1996.

- [52] Miller Puckette. Music 500: A new real-time digital synthesis system. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 1983. International Computer Music Association.
- [53] Miller Puckette. The m orchestra language. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 1984. International Computer Music Conference, International Computer Music Association.
- [54] Miller Puckette. The patcher. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, pages 420–429, San Francisco, 1988. International Computer Music Association.
- [55] Miller Puckette. Max at 17. *Computer Music Journal*, 26(4):31–43, Winter 2002.
- [56] Robert Gordon. A Calculated Look at Fixed-Point Arithmetic. <http://www.embedded.com/98/9804fe2.htm>, 2003.
- [57] P. Desain Roger B. Dannenberg and H. Honing. *Programming language design for music*. Lisse, Swets and Zeitlinger, 1997.
- [58] Carla Scaletti. Computer music, languages, kyma, and the future. *Computer Music Journal*, 26:69pp, Winter 2002.
- [59] E. Scheirer and B. Vercoe. Saol: The mpeg-4 structured audio orchestra language. *Computer Music Journal*, 23(2):31–51, 1999.
- [60] William Schottstaed and Rick Taube. Machine tongues XVII: CLM – music V meets common lisp. *Computer Music Journal*, 18(2):30–37, 1994.

- [61] William Schottstaedt. Pla: A composer's idea of a language. *Computer Music Journal*, 7(1):11–20, Winter 1983.
- [62] Robert W. Sebesta. *Concepts of Programming Languages*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, Reading, Mass., 1996.
- [63] J. O. Smith and P. Gossett. A flexible sampling-rate conversion method. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, volume 2, pages 19.4.1–19.4.2, New York, March 1984. IEEE Press.
- [64] Leland Smith. Score—a musician's approach to computer music. *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, 20:7–14, 1972.
- [65] Andrew Sorensen and Andrew Brown. jMusic – Music composition in Java. <http://jmusic.ci.qut.edu.au/>.
- [66] The Handhelds Project. Linux on the Compaq iPaq. <http://www.handhelds.org/>, 2000.
- [67] George Tzanetakis and Perry Cook. Marsyas a framework for audio analysis. *Organised Sound*, 4(3):169 – 175, 1999.
- [68] Todd Veldhuizen. Using C++ template metaprograms. *C++ Report*, 7(4):36–43, May 1995. Reprinted in *C++ Gems*, ed. Stanley Lippman.
- [69] Barry Vercoe. *Csound, a manual for the audio processing system*, 1992.
- [70] Ge Wang and Perry Cook. Chuck: A concurrent, on-the-fly, audio programming language. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 2003. Computer Music Association.

- [71] Brian P. Flannery William T. Vetterling. *Numerical Recipes in C++*. Cambridge University Press, 2002.
- [72] Matthew Wright and Adrian Freed. Open sound control: A new protocol for communicating with sound synthesizers. In *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, San Francisco, 1997. International Computer Music Association.
- [73] David Zicarelli. How i learned to love a program that does nothing. *Computer Music Journal*, 26(4):44–51, Winter 2002.